

E. Hitzer, Book review. G. Kuby, R. Spaemann (foreword), J. P. Kirchner (translation), *The Global Sexual Revolution: Destruction of Freedom in the Name of Freedom*, Angelico Press, Kettering, USA, 2015, *Sophia Journal of European Studies*: Vol. 11, pp. 125-135, 2019, Open Access: <https://digital-archives.sophia.ac.jp/repository/view/repository/20190529127>

Book review

G. Kuby, R. Spaemann (foreword), J. P. Kirchner (translation),
The Global Sexual Revolution: Destruction of Freedom in the Name of Freedom,
Angelico Press, Kettering, USA, 2015

Eckhard Hitzer

Abstract. German sociologist G. Kuby studies the historic, ideological, religious, linguistic, political, legal, educational, economic and social development of the global sexual revolution and its effects, a cultural revolution serving the goals of a small but unexpectedly influential LGBTI minority.

ドイツの社会学者 G.クビは歴史的、イデオロギー的、宗教的、言語的、政治的、法的、教育的、経済的、社会的な観点から、世界的な性の革命とその影響を考察している。この文化的な革命は、LGBTI マイノリティが予想以上の影響力をもつようになったことを表している。

In memory of my mother Eva Hitzer (30 Oct. 1926 - 19 Dec. 2018).

The German author Ms. Gabriele Kuby began to study sociology at Free University of Berlin in 1967 and completed her Masters degree under the guidance of Ralph Darendorf in Konstanz. She has already previously authored several books, some on related subjects. The German original is: *Die globale sexuelle Revolution: Zerstörung der Freiheit im Namen der Freiheit*, Fe-Medienverlags GmbH, 2012. For this American edition (of 283 pp.), the book has been updated, some material more relevant for European readers has been replaced by US relevant content. After the foreword by German philosopher Prof. Robert Spaemann follows an author preface. The book is structured into 16 Chapters and an afterword, an index of names and a mini biography of the author. Each Chapter is subdivided into sections, listed with page numbers in the table of contents. The back cover briefly describes the book, and includes 8 comments by prominent readers and experts. More detailed praise for the English and German editions are given on the first 4 pages of the book. For example, Pope Benedict XVI: “Mrs. Kuby is a brave warrior against ideologies that ultimately result in the destruction of man.”

Chapter (Chp.) 1 on The Destruction of Freedom in the Name of Freedom discusses the modern dismantling of sexuality in the name of gender mainstreaming, contrary to Art. 16 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which says: “The family is the natural and fundamental group unit of society and is entitled to protection by society and the State”. Sociological research has shown, that high culture correlates with high moral standards (J.D. Unwin, *Sex and Culture* (London: OUP, 1934)), but the author observes that today the dissolution of moral standards is being enforced. A massive gender ideology based cultural revolution seems to take place, which has the appearance of a new global form of soft totalitarianism. Criticism of this development in politics, academia, media, church, be it value, science or opinion based is purposely excluded from public discourse, stigmatized, criminalized and may lead to job loss. Criminalization tools are new anti-discrimination laws, and new offenses “homophobia” and “hate-speech”. Kuby sees a worrisome parallel to the Brave New World dictatorship of Aldous Huxley’s (1930) famous novel, in which sexual freedom compensates for horrible losses of political and economic freedom.

In Chp. 2 Kuby reviews history since the French Revolution. It began with Marquies de Sade’s

perverse sadomasochism, Voltaire's "Crush the infamy!" (the church), Malthusianistic reduction of world population, and continued with Margaret Sanger's eugenics movement (supported by president T. Roosevelt) the American Birth Control League backed by the Rockefellers, including J.D. Rockefeller III's personal contraception crusade commitment. The Birth Control League morphed 1942 into International Planned Parenthood (IPP), with its German branch euphemistically named Pro Familia, which performs 77% of all abortions in Germany. Marx' idea was to shatter the family: "The secret to the Holy Family is the earthly family. To make the former disappear, the latter must be destroyed, in theory and in practice." (p. 22). Engels saw monogamy as a male/female class oppression. Leninist Alexandra Kollontai's outmost efforts (legalizing abortion and divorce, promotion of free love) during the Russian Revolution to destroy the family and take state control of child rearing failed, and had to be reverted. In the Weimar Republic Wilhelm Reich saw total sexualization of culture as a way to exterminate churches and the traditional state. Later the Frankfurt School (Adorno, Horkheimer and Marcuse) dressed up Reich's ideas in their theories, succeeding in the 1960ies student uprisings. The homosexual Magnus Hirschfeld campaigned for abolition of the binary gender system, founded the Institute for Nudism (Institut für Freikörperkultur), and the World League for Sexual Reform. He advocated eugenics, and was a member of the German Society for Racial Hygiene. Nowadays the German federal government finances a foundation in his name to achieve "human rights for sexual minorities" (p. 27). Freudian theories played an eminent role in dismantling Christian values and [promoting](#) cultural sexualization. Freud's student C.G. Jung's psychology was described by Martin Buber as pseudo-religious Gnosticism, and he opened the door for esotericism in Christian spirituality. Kuby reviews the influences of John Watson's behaviorism based on Darwinism, Edward Barnay's social engineering (mass manipulation) tools of propaganda, further developed by Bernard Berelson (president of the Population Council under J.D. Rockefeller III). An important method was to recast sexual morality as a matter of opinion instead of a matter of religion. The "father of sexology" Alfred Kinsey was a homosexual sadomasochist, who obviously obtained "scientific" data through criminal sexual abuse of children. John Money promoted free gender choice and supported this by a case of sex reassignment surgery of an infant twin boy (then named Brenda), which lead to suicidal thoughts of the boy at 11, and decisive return to life as a boy at age 13, suicide at age 38, and suicide of his brother 2 years earlier. Money advocated group sex, bisexuality, and fucking games for children. Simone de Beauvoir famously wrote "One is not born, but rather becomes a woman," (p. 34) in her book 'The Second Sex'. Denial of feminine identity should lead to the same privileges as man. Beauvoir started a campaign of extolling abortion (she had two herself), this lead eventually to today's killing of children in the womb free of prosecution, more than 8 million children have been aborted in Germany, and 56 million in the US. Later Judith Butler (further described in Chp. 3) introduced the ideology of gender mainstreaming, which denies biological gender differences between man and woman and aims at their "destruction in society" (p. 35, line 26). Rockefeller and Berelson influenced President Johnson to say (1965): "I will seek new ways to use our knowledge to help deal with the explosion of world population and the growing scarcity in world resources" (p. 35). Next Kuby reviews the influence of the Frankfurt School on the 1960ies student uprising with slogans like "Battle the bourgeois nuclear family! If you sleep with the same one twice, you're a slave to bourgeois vice!" (p. 38). In this time the media eagerly portrayed sex with anyone – in front of, with and among children – of the Berlin Communes. In Hollywood the Motion Picture Production Code fell, Playboy entered business, hashish and psychedelic drugs became acceptable. ... Sexualization blinds people: "Blindness of the mind is the first-born daughter of lust." (T.

Aquinas, p. 40). The legal deregulation of Sexuality in Germany (similar to other Western countries) is reviewed from the 1961 authorization of the birth control pill to the permission of same sex partner adoption of an adopted child of one partner (2001).

Chp. 3 describes in some detail, how the modern gender ideology grew out of the traditional feminist fight for equal rights. This ideology envisions a deconstruction (term different from p. 35, line 26) and elimination of binary sexuality (p. 44, lines 2, 5 and 14)-. Its modern form is the subversive gender theory of Judith Butler, professor of rhetoric at University of California, Berkeley, and since 2006 at the European Graduate School of Switzerland. She lives as a lesbian. For Butler there is no masculine or feminine being, only a certain performance, a behavior that can change at any time. For her “the ‘doer’ is variably constructed in and through the deed.” (p. 46). This gender theory has become very influential. In Germany, government financed gender competence centers watch over its political implementation, and at universities gender/queer studies have been established and expanded. Gender ideology shapes the staff of public authorities, corporations and educational institutions. Even while the public hardly knows what gender theory is, it has become mainstream. Chp. 4 on the globalization of the sexual revolution by the UN, opens with a memorable quote by C.S. Lewis “The power of Man to make himself what he pleases means, as we have seen, the power of some men to make other men what they please.” (p. 49). The UN started out in 1948 with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, derived from the biblical revelation in Genesis 1:27: “God created mankind in his image; in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them.” Kuby reviews how postmodernism fills old expressions with new contents: Truth → Right to error, Sex → Gender, Binary sexual identity as man or woman → Choice of gender, Ten Commandments → Moral relativism, God → The autonomous individual, etc. An intentional change of language is revealed in Chp. 8 as a political strategy. Nowadays the UN via its UN Fund for Population Activities (UNFPA) is devoted to population control, including the sterilization of 300,000 poor Peruvian women under dictator Alberto Fujimori and involvement in China’s brutal one-child-policy. Kuby analyzes the development of US and UN agency “reproductive health services“, a cover up for “safe” abortion and sterilization, in the action plan of the 1995 UN World Conference on Woman in Beijing. The UN continued with strong US support to campaign for “reproductive rights” at the 1994 UN Population Conference in Cairo, where US vice-president Al Gore claimed that “all of the Third World’s problems stemmed from overpopulation” (p. 57). This is in full agreement with super-rich multi-billionaires like D. Rockefeller, B. Gates, T. Turner, G. Soros, M. Bloomberg, and W. Buffet in *The Good Club*. Stephen Mosher, president of the Population Research Institute comments: “They [UNFPA] tell us that too many babies are being born to poor people in developing countries. This is tantamount to saying that only the wealthy should be allowed to have children, and is a new form of global racism.-” (p. 58,59). Kuby shows how the 1995 UN World Conference on Woman in Beijing was prepared and manipulated by the Women’s Environment and Development Organization (WEDO) and IPP Federation. A flyer distributed in the end by the coalition for families described the final conference document as: “The document doesn’t respect human dignity, seeks to destroy the family, totally ignores marriage, minimizes the importance of motherhood, seeks to impose depraved sexual attitudes, promotes homosexuality, lesbianism, sexual promiscuity, and sex for children and seeks to destroy the authority of parents over the children.” (p. 60). The UN is seen to campaign for an international “human” right to abortion. The Network Conference of Glen Cove (1996) agreed to use treaty-monitoring bodies for converting soft norms into hard laws, giving the false impression that reproductive and sexual health rights were binding human rights.

In Chp. 5 Kuby outlines how a group of “renowned human rights experts” formulated in 2007 at a conference in Yogyakarta, Indonesia, 29 principles, each beginning with “THE STATES SHALL ...” (p. 65). These principles clearly show the goals, methods of obfuscation, enforcement and global implementation of the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transsexual, Intersexual (LGBTI) agenda, taking a totalitarian approach. Opposition is sanctioned by curtailment of freedom of contract, of freedom of speech, suppression of non-compliant information, and criminalization of opposition.

Chp. 6 shows how the EU joined the gender bandwagon. Regarding the pressure of the European Parliament for homosexual unions with adoption rights, Pope John Paul II commented: “It is legitimate and even necessary to ask whether this is not the work of another ideology of evil, more insidious and hidden, perhaps, intent on exploiting human rights themselves against man and against the family.” (p. 82). According to the EU constitution principle of subsidiarity marriage and family politics should be reserved for member states. Yet the EU takes tax payers’ money to massively fund LGBTI lobby organizations like International Lesbian and Gay Alliance (ILGA) with almost 70%, still regarding it an independent “NGO”. In 2000 the EU adopted The Charter of Fundamental Rights for the EU, which deletes the explicit mention of men and women when defining the rights of marriage and family. In the 1999 Amsterdam Treaty the EU adopted the term “sexual orientation” as new criterion for protection against discrimination. What this means practically can be easily seen in the activities of the EU’s General Directorates. In strategic litigations the European Court of Justice (ECJ) and the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) have come to play key roles, accompanied by newly founded EU agencies, The Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA) in Vienna, and the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) in Vilnius, both since 2007. Analysis of resolutions of the European Parliament and the Council of Europe since 1999 show, how strongly these bodies back the LGBTI agenda. The EU is intent on carrying this agenda beyond Europe, as e.g. shown in 2010 by the Working Party on Human Rights approval of the “Toolkit to Promote and Protect the Enjoyment of all Human Rights by Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender (LGBT) People” (p. 90). The EU deliberately deregulates sexual norms.

Chp. 7 presents Case Studies of the Gender Revolution: The Gender Package includes deconstruction of bipolar sexual identity, battle against homosexual normativity, abortion as human right, sexualization of children by mandatory sex education, impoverishment of families. Gender mainstreaming is politically implemented away from the public eye in a strict top down approach, G. Kuby lists major steps of this implementation. The German Gender Manifesto (2006) is directed against “religious or socio-biological determinist approaches” that hold to “pre-discursive factors such as the will of God or genetic determination.” (p. 97). Prodded by the UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Woman, the German Ethics Council recommend to introduce for 0.01% of the population a “third gender”, whose biological characteristics are ambiguous. German state politicians (NRW) decide to “gender” society. Scientific criticism is suppressed, like that of criminologist Prof. Dr. Michael Bock, who finds that both for the totalitarian regimes of the 20th century and for gender mainstreaming with their “total will to subordinate the entire social reality to a uniform principle or to penetrate it with this principle [this] is the reason these regimes are called “totalitarian”.” (p. 101). Further cases are gender conferences, gendering of justice, of education K-12, and political parties.

Chp. 8 reviews the political rape of language by the corruption of words, illustrated with ideological key terms like parent 1 and parent 2 for mother and father. Feminists try to gender language by pairing Bürger und Bürgerinnen, but rejecting Terroristen und Terroristinnen.

Chp. 9 looks into the new global scourge of pornography, which seems to have become a completely

normal annual 97 billion dollar business, degrading alike the perpetrators, victims and consumers, driving the latter into addiction, escalation, desensitization and finally to acting out sexually, substantiated by evidence from modern brain research on resulting brain changes. Destruction ensues for marriage, family, children and youth, yet general ignorance seems to prevail.

Chp. 10 discusses how the homosexual movement managed to bring the American Psychological Association to take homosexuality from its list of mental illnesses entitled for treatment, including egodystonic homosexuality. Government survey's show, that only 1.6% of the US population identify as homosexual. The causes of homosexuality are investigated, as well as its hazards of physical and mental illnesses, its highly promiscuous nature, relation to sexual abuse, and the possibility to change to heterosexuality. Registered civil unions of homosexuals are only taken advantage of by a mere 2% of homosexuals, by a minority of a minority, even though media propaganda tries to make belief homosexual marriage is a new human right. In the context of child adoption by homosexual couples the right of children to their parents is denied. The term homophobia is created on purpose to defame opposition to homosexuality and deregulation of sexual norms.

Chp. 11 investigates the intrinsic antagonism between Christian belief and homosexuality. In ethically monotheistic Judaism homosexuality was outlawed (Lev.18:22, 20:13). Kuby quotes D. Prager: "What I have not understood is why [modern] Jews or Christians would join the assault [on family life]. I do know. They do not know what is at stake." (p. 177). The Biblical order of creation is reviewed, including the analogy between family love and Trinitarian love, prophet Elijah's public conflict with priests of the pagan fertility gods of sexual excess Baal and Asherah, the prophet Hosea, Jesus Christ's teaching on marriage, apostolic teaching on sexual moral and order and meaning of marriage. Next is Pope John Paul II's "Theology of the Body to announce human love as part of God's plan of salvation" (pp. 182,183) and how churches have come under pressure from the global sexual revolution, targeting the core Christian answer to "What is man?" (p. 184). Examples are the Anglican church, Lutheran church (shifting in 20 years from biblical rejection of homosexuality to legalized homosexual concubinage in the rectories in Germany), and Catholic church (revealing, e.g., that the child abuse problem in the church is overwhelmingly "not a pedophilia problem but a homosexuality problem" (p. 192)). Kuby goes on to dismantle theological sophistry favoring homosexuality and alerts to the trivialization of Biblical notions of love, referring to Pope Benedict XVI's *Deus Caritas Est* and D. Bonhoeffer's warning against "cheap" grace as "deadly enemy of our Church" (p. 196). The chapter ends with a brief excursus on Pope Paul VI's defense of the sanctity of life before the UN Assembly, his encyclical on birth control *Humanae Vitae*, and Western church crisis out of lack of support for the encyclical.

Chp. 12 analyzes how mandatory comprehensive manipulative sex education is brought into K-12 education. Family and sexual moral traditions need to be passed on (Latin *tradere*) or be lost. Since the 1970s in German schools a progression from information to education to indoctrination, resulting in complete demoralization of sexuality took place, undermining the parents' rights (The Univ. Decl. Hum. Rs., Art. 16.3, and similarly ECHR and Lisbon Treaty) to raise their children as they see fit (p. 201). It is a result of the 1968 student revolts' demand of "sexual liberation" (p. 202) reaching power of legislation and government-financed programs in all Western countries, the UN and the EU. Individuals and organizations involved and their activities are characterized. One such organization, the International Planned Parenthood Federation (IPPF) prides itself in 2010 in a total of 180 countries to have "22 million pregnancies averted" (p. 204), while in 2015 being found to sell intact fetal body parts from illegal partial-birth abortions. IPPF further claims falsely that access to safe

legal abortion is a public health and human rights imperative. IPPF abortion programs in developing countries are found to be financed by the EU without legal basis. A main target group of IPPF are teenagers. Germany's IPPF branch Pro Familia claims to conduct 77 percent of all German pregnancy terminations in its six abortion centers, but is still a charitable organization exempt from taxes (p. 206). Then follows an exposition of the contents and methods of comprehensive sex education, as promoted by the IPPF, its instrumentalization of the World Association of Girl Scouts and Girl Guides, and in Europe by the WHO and the German Federal Center for Health Education (BZgA). Next the issue of sexual abuse of children and teenagers, its consequences and the failure of prevention by forced sex education are reviewed. A further discussion of the methods and risks of manipulative sexualization of children and teenagers follows, with details on the risks of teen pregnancy and abortion, health damage from contraceptives, infection with sexual diseases, psychological injury that can lead to depression and suicide, lower (academic) achievement, and weakened ability to bond. Twelve reasons to stop sexualization of children by the state are given, ranging from first "Deregulation of sexuality leads to cultural decay" (based on J. Unwin's sociological research) to twelfth "The demographic crisis is a result of separating sexuality from fertility" (with Germany's 2009 birthrate of 1.36 per couple the lowest in Europe and the lowest ever). Finally, inconsistencies in the arguments of sexual revolutionaries and the resulting damage are exposed, and the question is asked who gains from the normative deregulation of sexuality?²

Chp. 13 looks into the relationship of the Catholic church and comprehensive sex education, into reality and ideals. The first section details how many main stream Catholic organizations (Social Service for Catholic Women, Caritas, Catholic Youth Community, Donum Vitae) have gone wrong in promoting comprehensive sex education toward hedonistic sexuality, instead of putting the guidelines of the encyclical *Humanae Vitae* into practice. Next the Catholic principles for education for love are briefly expounded, with the virtue of chastity ("The successful integration of sexuality within the person and thus the inner unity of man in his bodily and spiritual being", p. 236) being a key concept. Relevant theological documents published under John Paul II are indicated, and in particular the 1995 "The Truth and Meaning of Human Sexuality" (p. 236) is reviewed in some detail, quoting e.g., "Chastity is the spiritual power which frees love from selfishness and aggression. ... Chastity includes an apprenticeship in self-mastery which is a training in human freedom." (p. 237). Particular attention is paid to the parents' rights and obligation to raise their children. Finally a connection is drawn between the lofty ideals of the Catholic teaching on love, and the integrity, appeal and luster of Catholic schools.

Chp. 14 with representative examples investigates how the following freedoms are increasingly endangered by the worldwide LGBTI agenda: Freedom of religion / conscience / expression / speech / assembly / judiciary / science / therapy / economy / contract / parents. For example, Anthony Priddis, Anglican bishop of Hereford, UK, had to pay over £47,000 for his unwillingness to hire active homosexuals for youth work, had to participate in "equal opportunity training" and pay rejected applications £7,000 for psychiatric injury and £6,000 for injury of feelings. In the UK all Catholic adoption agencies had to close, because they would only place children with married heterosexual couples.

Chp. 15 shows some cases of civil resistance to the top down sexual revolution. Christian churches, NGOs, individuals and institutions work for human dignity, life, marriage and family. The Spanish socialist José L.A. Zapatero government (2004-2011) passed a multitude of laws "with the goal of destroying the old order ... [and to] change the lives of the individual." (p. 260), including legalization of homosexual "marriage". In 2005, over 2 million Spaniards protested in favor of the

family, against homosexual “marriage”. Pope Benedict XVI visited Spain three times (2006-2010). In Jan. 2012 the new government of conservative Mariano Rajoy abolished gender indoctrination in Spanish schools (labeled Educación para la Ciudadanía). In Hungary the conservative government created a new constitution in 2012, recognizing God, the family, “marriage as life partnership between a man and a woman” (p. 261), the right of life of unborn children from conception, and banning human cloning and body part trade. EU criticism is countered by attorney Dr. Eva Maria Barki, writing that the EU lacks in democracy, because it “is still not signed on to the European Convention for Human Rights; its bodies can therefore not be prosecuted before the European court of Human Rights.” (p. 262). Further examples come from France, Germany, Switzerland, Slovakia, Poland, Croatia, Norway, the EU, and the US. There the Obama government through the Health and Human Services mandate forced “all employers to offer insured workers prescription contraceptives, the “morning-after pill”, and sterilization free of charge.” (p. 265, 266). As part of the resistance, 13 US state attorneys general announced legal action, because they saw an “impermissible violation of the Constitution’s First Amendment virtually unparalleled in American history.” (p. 266). Finally, beginning with Swiss bishop Dr. Vitus Huonder’s 2013 declaration on “Gender: The Deep Falsehood of a Theory” (p. 267), bishops and bishop’s conferences, and Pope Benedict XVI speak “out against genderism and the sexualization of children.” (p. 267). Benedict XVI said: “... The manipulation of nature, which we deplore today where our environment is concerned, now becomes man’s fundamental choice where he himself is concerned ...” (p. 268).

Chp. 16 shows how we are on a slippery slope to a new totalitarianism. Former German constitutional judge Ernst-Wolfgang Böckenförde famously said that a liberal state can only survive “if the freedom it [a state] grants its citizens is regulated from the inside through the moral substance of the individual” (p. 275). Pope Benedict wrote: “An acquired blindness to guilt, the numbing of the conscience ... is a more dangerous illness of the soul, as guilt is still recognized as guilt.” (p. 276). In her final paragraph in the afterword G. Kuby writes: “It is worthwhile to work toward a spiritual and moral renewal of Europe, which has its unique culture largely thanks to Christianity – the true source of individual and political freedom.” (p. 280)

In face of the fundamental changes of human values, morals, ethics, rights and demography we are currently facing globally, G. Kuby’s book tries to inform about what caused this development, and what are its current and expected future effects. Such a critical stance as Kuby presents gives us a valuable opportunity to rethink about the current trends. Without boring the reader she quotes, analyzes and interprets a wide variety of events, documents, original data, proclamations and scientific studies. Despite of its depth, the book succeeds to consistently address non-specialists in fairly comprehensible language. The book does not just argue from a Christian moral perspective, it gathers and presents evidence of general interest. Beyond the European-American scope of the book, it would be interesting to learn more on how the LGBTI movement promotes its agenda in Africa and Asia. I warmly recommend this book to all interested in this issue.

E. Hitzer, Book review. G. Kuby, R. Spaemann (forward), J. P. Kirchner (translation), *The Global Sexual Revolution: Destruction of Freedom in the Name of Freedom*, Angelico Press, Kettering, USA, 2015, *Sophia Journal of European Studies*: Vol. 11, pp. 125-135, 2019, Open Access: <https://digital-archives.sophia.ac.jp/repository/view/repository/20190529127>